

Stercoral Peritonitis Revealing Post-Traumatic Rectal Perforation: A Case Report

Maria Benzakour ✉

Department of Anesthesia Resuscitation, p33 Chu Ibn Rochd, Casablanca, Morocco

Iddbaha Youssef

Department of Anesthesia Resuscitation, p33 Chu Ibn Rochd, Casablanca, Morocco

Khalid Khaleq

Department of Anesthesia Resuscitation, p33 Chu Ibn Rochd, Casablanca, Morocco

Laabouli Rida

Department of Visceral Surgery, Casablanca, Morocco

Fadli Yasser

Department of Anesthesia Resuscitation, p33 Chu Ibn Rochd, Casablanca, Morocco

Majd Abdssamad

Department of Visceral Surgery, Casablanca, Morocco

Khalid El Hattabi

Department of Visceral Surgery, Casablanca, Morocco

Abstract

Open abdominal trauma can be complicated by serious digestive injuries, often delayed in their presentation. We report the case of a 49-year-old man, victim of a road traffic accident with hypogastric impact, who presented with stercoral peritonitis secondary to an unrecognized rectal perforation. The initially stable evolution quickly required emergency surgery with rectal suture, peritoneal cleansing and protective colostomy. This case illustrates the importance of early surgical exploration in the face of any clinical doubt after abdominal trauma.

Introduction

Open abdominal trauma is a common emergency in intensive care and surgery departments. It often results from road traffic accidents or violent assaults and can cause serious visceral injuries, sometimes hidden on initial imaging. Rectal perforation in this context is rare, due to the retroperitoneal location of the rectum, but it can occur during direct pelvic trauma. When it goes unnoticed, it can progress to stercoral peritonitis, a severe complication associated with a high morbidity and mortality rate. We report here the case of a patient who suffered open abdominal trauma and progressed to stercoral peritonitis secondary to an unrecognized rectal perforation, requiring emergency multidisciplinary management.

Case Presentation

A 49-year-old man with no known medical history was admitted for emergency surgery 12 hours after a road traffic accident with direct impact to the abdomen,

following a collision with a horse-drawn carriage. The initial examination revealed a 2 cm open abdominal wound in the hypogastric region with clean edges, without exteriorization of viscera or digestive or urinary fluids, as well as a 3 cm penile wound with jagged edges.

The patient was conscious (GCS 15/15), hemodynamically stable (BP 130/60 mmHg, HR 80 bpm), eupneic, and afebrile. Abdominal examination revealed a guarding localized to both iliac fossae and the hypogastrium. Rectal examination showed a finger cot soiled with normal-colored stools, without palpable breach. Laboratory assessment revealed hemoglobin at 15.7 g/dl, leukocytes at 3570/mm³, platelets at 294000/mm³, and CRP at 13.5 mg/L. Abdominal CT scan showed a medium-abundance peritoneal effusion, without traumatic injury to solid organs.

More Information

How to cite this article: Benzakour M, Youssef I, Khaleq K, Rida L, Yasser F, Abdssamad M, El Hattabi K. Stercoral Peritonitis Revealing Post-Traumatic Rectal Perforation: A Case Report. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(4):65-7.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(4).12

Keywords:

Stercoral peritonitis,
Rectal perforation,
Abdominal trauma,
Acute abdomen,
Emergency surgery.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

a)

b)

Figure 1: a), b). Image Showing a 2 cm Open Abdominal Wound in the Hypogastric Region

Figure 2: Abdominal CT Scan Showed a Medium-Sized Peritoneal Effusion

Given the discrepancy between imaging and clinical symptoms, surgical exploration was performed, revealing abundant hemoperitoneum, agglutination of small bowel loops at the level of the pouch of Douglas sealing a 3 cm anterior perforation of the rectum with contused edges, and false peritoneal membranes. Peritoneal cleansing was performed, followed by suturing of the perforation, a terminalized lateral protective colostomy, and pelvic and pre-vesical drainage. Intraoperative urological exploration did not reveal any bladder or urethral lesions.

Figure 3: Intraoperative Image of 3 cm Anterior Perforation of the Rectum

The patient was admitted to the postoperative intensive care unit, receiving broad-spectrum empirical antibiotics, sedation, mechanical ventilation, vasopressors (NA 2 mg/h), and close monitoring. The outcome was favorable with amine withdrawal and delayed extubation after hemodynamic stabilization.

Discussion

Post-traumatic stercoral peritonitis is a serious, rare, but potentially fatal complication that can result from undiagnosed colonic or rectal perforation after abdominal trauma. In the reported case, the absence of digestive exteriorization and nonspecific clinical signs initially masked the severity of the rectal injury, a diagnostic pitfall well described in the literature. The anatomical peculiarity of the rectum, located largely in the retroperitoneum, complicates lesion diagnosis, especially in the absence of obvious pneumoperitoneum or frank effusion on imaging. In this context, the sensitivity of abdominal CT scans remains moderate for small or plugged lesions. Thus, a discrepancy between imaging and clinical signs should suggest an occult digestive injury and prompt early surgical exploration. Digital rectal examination, although sometimes neglected, remains a crucial clinical examination in pelvic trauma. The mere presence of blood or stool on the finger cot may be sufficient to suspect rectal involvement, even in the absence of a palpable breach. Management of rectal perforation relies on rapid surgical management including peritoneal lavage, primary closure of the breach (if technically feasible), and placement of a

discharging colostomy in a septic environment. This latter procedure remains controversial in some elective settings, but is widely recommended in situations of severe contamination to limit the risk of sepsis or fistula. In terms of resuscitation, rapid control of the septic source is an absolute priority, in accordance with the recommendations of the Surviving Sepsis Campaign Guidelines. The use of broad-spectrum probabilistic antibiotic therapy, early use of vasopressors in case of shock, and mechanical ventilation if necessary, are part of the overall strategy for managing secondary septic shock [7]. Finally, this situation underlines the importance of a multidisciplinary approach involving digestive surgeons, intensive care specialists and sometimes urologists or gynecologists, depending on the location of the wounds. Postoperative follow-up includes regular clinical, biological and radiological assessment, as well as planning for colonic reintegration after resolution of sepsis [8].

Conclusion

This case illustrates the diagnostic pitfalls and progressive risks associated with open abdominal trauma, particularly in the presence of hypogastric wounds. Rectal perforation can be missed clinically and radiologically, progressing to rapidly destabilizing stercoral peritonitis. Early diagnosis, rapid surgical decision-making, and intensive intensive care are the keys to a favorable prognosis. This type of situation highlights the importance of multidisciplinary collaboration between surgeons, intensive care

specialists, and urologists to improve the chances of survival of these critically ill patients.

References

- [1] Kauvar DS, Wade CE. *The epidemiology and modern management of traumatic hemorrhage: US and international perspectives*. Crit Care. 2005;9 Suppl 5(Suppl 5):S1–S9.
- [2] Poletti PA, Mirvis SE, Shanmuganathan K. *Blunt abdominal trauma patients: can organ injury be excluded without performing computed tomography?*. 2004 Nov;57(5):1072-81.
- [3] Kumar A, Bansal VK, Khatri A, et al. *Evaluation of rectal injuries in trauma: clinical clues and the role of imaging*. J Emerg Trauma Shock. 2013;6(3):411-416.
- [4] G C Velmahos 1, E Degiannis, M Wells, I Souter, R Saadia. *Early closure of colostomies in trauma patients--a prospective randomized trial*. 1995 Nov;118(5):815-20.
- [5] J E Sola 1, J S Bender, T G Buchman. *Morbidity and timing of colostomy closure in trauma patients*. 1993 Aug;24(7):438-40.
- [6] Evans L, Rhodes A, Alhazzani W, et al. *Surviving Sepsis Campaign: International Guidelines for Management of Sepsis and Septic Shock 2021*. Crit Care Med. 2021;49(11):e1063–e1143.
- [7] Levy MM, Evans LE, Rhodes A. *The Surviving Sepsis Campaign Bundle: 2018 update*. Crit Care Med. 2018 Jun;44(6):925-928.
- [8] Adam Fields 1, Ali Salim. *Contemporary diagnosis and management of colorectal injuries: What you need to know*. 2024 Oct 1;97(4):497-504.

